

Enhancing stimulated Brillouin scattering in suspended silicon waveguides through subwavelength nanostructuring [Invited]

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Abstract: Brillouin optomechanics is playing a key role in the development of groundbreaking devices and novel functionalities in integrated silicon photonics, such as narrow linewidth filtering and lasers, tunable frequency, non-reciprocity, etc. Most silicon-based optomechanical waveguides, which use anchoring arms or perforated slabs to ensure mechanical stability and operate for transverse-electric polarized light, face challenges with acoustic mode leakage into the lateral Si slab, limiting the photon-phonon overlap and the Brillouin gain. Here, we propose new waveguide designs based on subwavelength nanostructuring to tailor near-infrared photons and GHz phonons and maximize the Brillouin gain. We introduce six different geometries suitable for both membrane or fully suspended configurations (i.e., without transversal arms anchoring the core to the Si slab). Our three-dimensional optomechanical simulations predict that subwavelength silicon membranes with strip, slot, and SWG slot core waveguides achieve gains up to $12257 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ at mechanical frequencies of 12-13 GHz. Moreover, suspended silicon waveguides with SWG slots achieve a high gain of $43542 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ at 4.45 GHz, with the ability to adjust the mechanical frequency from 4 to 9 GHz. Further enhancements in the Brillouin gain are studied by integrating side arms to amplify the moving boundaries effect in the suspended SWG slot waveguides and leveraging the slow light regime, which can significantly increase the Brillouin gain up to $17 \times 10^6 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ for a mechanical mode at 11.18 GHz.

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1. Introduction

Over a century has passed since Léon Brillouin first elucidated the inelastic scattering of light by acoustic waves [1]. This third-order nonlinear process coherently couples optical waves in the near-infrared spectrum with acoustic waves in the GHz frequency range, exhibiting some disruptive features. These include a low activation power threshold (significantly lower than that required for Kerr and Raman effects), narrow spectral linewidth ranging from kHz to MHz, adjustable frequency shifts, optical reconfiguration capabilities, and selective introduction of gain or loss [2]. Despite its early discovery, it was not until recent decades that Brillouin scattering (BS) garnered significant attention for its potential in pioneering applications such as microscopy, distributed optical sensing, signal generation and processing, and microwave photonics [3–7]. Strides in stimulated Brillouin scattering (SBS) were predominantly propelled by electrostriction forces in bulk media and traditional step-index optical fibers. Still, this paradigm shifted with recent breakthroughs in nanofabrication techniques [8–10]. Enhanced Brillouin interactions were predicted in nanophotonic waveguides, particularly those with high refractive index contrasts, due

to the high modal confinement and the combined action of electrostriction and intense radiation pressure at the waveguide boundaries [11,12].

The first observation of on-chip SBS using planar waveguides was demonstrated in chalcogenide As_2S_3 rib waveguides surrounded by silica cladding to ensure the confinement of both photons and phonons [13]. The main limitation of this type of chalcogenide waveguide is the difficulty of integration with well-established silicon photonic material platforms; hence, alternative composites and integration with germano-silicates are currently being investigated [14,15]. Other materials that have been considered for SBS include lithium niobate and AlGaAs. While lithium niobate suffers from weak phonon confinement [16,17], AlGaAs offers a high index contrast, low optical propagation loss, and good phonon confinement when used on a silica substrate. Despite these promising attributes, the latter is a relatively new platform that necessitates further refinement to achieve its full potential [18]. Employing high-Q resonators constructed from silica or calcium fluoride is also a promising approach to amplify Brillouin gain [19,20]. However, this solution implies bulky sizes, which may limit their practicality in certain applications.

Silicon-on-insulator (SOI) is a mature technology platform employed in a broad spectrum of photonic applications. Being aligned with CMOS fabrication processes, it offers many advantages over the aforementioned alternative materials, such as large-scale manufacturing and low cost [21]. Nevertheless, SOI was initially overlooked for SBS as it is unable to effectively confine phonons inside conventional Si waveguides. The problem arises from the higher stiffness of the Si waveguide compared to the SiO_2 buried layer, which prevents total internal reflection of the acoustic mode and results in phonon leakage from the Si waveguide to the buried oxide (BOX) layer. The main strategy to overcome this constraint involves isolating the phonon pathway towards the SiO_2 by suspending the Si waveguide (removal of SiO_2 below through HF acid) or using phoxonic crystals [22–24]. The initial demonstration of SBS in silicon took place in 2013 using a suspended membrane consisting of a central Si waveguide supported by silicon nitride (SiN) arms. The SBS gain was restricted to $2.7 \times 10^3 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ in experiments due to suboptimal photon-phonon coupling [22]. A different strategy was proposed a couple of years later using a thin SiO_2 pedestal to support the Si waveguide and reduce the phonon leakage into the BOX. This strategy resulted in a measured SBS gain of $3 \times 10^3 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$, but at the cost of more complex fabrication and reduced mechanical robustness [25]. To reduce optical propagation losses and improve mechanical stability, rib waveguides were proposed as Brillouin active systems achieving only slightly lower gains ($10^3 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$) because of the weak photon-phonon overlap [26]. To overcome this constraint, suspended ridge waveguides surrounded by a 1D phononic crystal were subsequently proposed [27]. Suspended anti-resonant acoustic waveguides with enhanced coupling strength were demonstrated yielding Brillouin gains of $3.5 \times 10^3 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ [28]. Conversely, phoxonic crystals that exhibit simultaneous photonic and phononic bandgaps have been posited to attain higher Brillouin gains in theory, with values reaching up to $10^6 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ [29]. Still, these structures are inherently limited by narrow operating bandwidth and high optical propagation losses. Moreover, Håkansson *et al.* reported on the genetic optimization of several waveguide geometries that achieved simulated gains of $10^8 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ [30]. These designs, however, target low mechanical frequency ranges, specifically in the MHz order, and are based on intricate shapes that may pose significant challenges during the fabrication process.

The nanostructuring of silicon photonic wires at the subwavelength scale, i.e., with a period shorter than half of the effective wavelength of the light propagating through the structure, has been an essential tool for designing several groundbreaking devices [31–34]. In this type of waveguides, reflection and radiation effects are suppressed, and light propagates through the periodic waveguide ideally without losses like it would in an equivalent homogeneous waveguide. In addition, subwavelength waveguides provide flexible confinement and dispersion engineering non-feasible in conventional strip and rib waveguides, with much lower propagation loss and wider bandwidth than photonic crystals. Recently, the additional degrees of freedom provided by

these periodic structures have also been exploited to engineer Brillouin interactions [35] because: i) near-infrared photons and GHz phonons in silicon have similar wavelength [36]. Thus, the same structuration operates in the subwavelength regime for light and sound; and ii) engineering the longitudinal and transversal subwavelength geometries allows independent control of photonic and phononic modes. An optomechanical Si waveguide for SBS in the mid-infrared (at 4 μm optical wavelength) was proposed based on a rectangular core suspended in air by an array of ribs, where each rib is patterned in the transverse direction to create a phononic mirror and avoid the transmission of the acoustic waves to the substrate [37]. Based on this approach and using three different etch steps, a simulated Brillouin gain of $1750 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ was achieved for a mechanical frequency of 3.35 GHz. A year later, Zhang *et al.* proposed a suspended silicon membrane waveguide that confines the optical mode through a subwavelength grating (SWG) cladding while the same nanostructuring reduced the leakage of the acoustic modes through mechanical softening [38]. Employing this strategy that requires two etch steps, a calculated Brillouin gain of $3500 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ was achieved for a mechanical mode at a high frequency of 9 GHz. To further reduce the number of etch steps to a single one, genetic optimization was applied to the design of subwavelength-structured silicon membranes, yielding a calculated Brillouin gain of $3300 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ for a remarkable mechanical frequency near 15 GHz [39]. A suspended waveguide relying on the combination of a subwavelength cladding followed by a phononic crystal was also proposed attaining a Brillouin gain of $2046 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ for a mechanical mode near 7.2 GHz [40]. Despite these promising solutions, the enhancement of the Brillouin gain remains one of the main challenges in subwavelength-structured Si waveguides.

In this work, we propose six different SWG-based structures that require a single-etch step to optimize Brillouin gain. We harness subwavelength nanostructuring to suspend the waveguides and control the distribution of optical and mechanical modes. Different geometries that can be used either in membrane or fully suspended configuration (i.e., without transversal arms anchoring the core to the Si slab) are proposed. According to three-dimensional (3D) multi-physics optomechanical simulations, the best waveguide geometries achieve a Brillouin gain of $12 \cdot 10^3 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ (12.7 GHz mechanical frequency) and $17 \cdot 10^6 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ (11.2 GHz mechanical frequency) for membrane and suspended waveguides, respectively.

2. Principle

For the design of the subwavelength-engineered waveguides, we focus on intramodal forward stimulated Brillouin scattering (FSBS). In this configuration, pump and scattered light co-propagate in the same direction and the same optical mode (i.e., identical mode order and polarization) and couple to a specific mechanical mode. The energy conservation and phase-matching conditions to be met for FSBS are [2,41]:

$$\omega_p \pm \Omega = \omega_s, \quad (1)$$

$$k_p(\omega_p) - q(\Omega) = k_s(\omega_s), \quad (2)$$

where $k_p(\omega_p)$ and $k_s(\omega_s)$ are the optical wavevectors of the pump and the forward-scattered light at angular frequencies ω_p and ω_s , respectively, q is the wavevector of the mechanical mode and Ω is its angular frequency. Since $\omega_p \approx \omega_s \gg \Omega$ and both pump and scattered light propagate in the same spatial mode, Eq. (2) can be approximated to $q(\Omega) \approx 0$. Thus, in FSBS the mechanical mode is near the cut-off frequency and resembles a transverse mechanical resonance in the waveguide, i.e., it takes the form of a transversal breathing-like mode with a very low phase velocity. It should be noted that the wavevector of the mechanical mode can be rigorously calculated as $q(\Omega) = \pm\Omega/v_g$, where $v_g = c/n_g$ is the optical group velocity.

The performance of Brillouin-active waveguides is typically evaluated through the Brillouin gain (G_B), as it is usually more relevant than other optomechanical figures of merits [29,40]. The

Brillouin gain coefficient can be calculated as [12,38,41–44]:

$$G_B = \frac{2\omega_p Q_m}{P_p P_s \bar{m}_{\text{eff}} \Omega^2 u_m^2 \Lambda} | \int f_{\text{MB}} dA + \int f_{\text{PE}} dV |^2 \mathcal{L}(\Omega). \quad (3)$$

Here, $\mathcal{L}(\Omega)$ is the Lorentzian spectrum, and P_p and P_s account for the optical power of the pump and the forward-scattered field [38]:

$$P_{i=p,s} = \left(\int \mathbf{E}_i \times \mathbf{H}_i^* \cdot \hat{z} dA \right) / 2. \quad (4)$$

Moreover, \bar{m}_{eff} is the effective mass given by $\bar{m}_{\text{eff}} = \int \rho / \Lambda | \mathbf{u} |^2 / | u_m |^2 dV$, with \mathbf{u} being the displacement, u_m the maximum of the displacement and ρ the density. The contribution of the moving boundaries (MB) and photoelastic (PE) effects in Eq. (3) is represented by the area and volume overlap integrals of the force densities, respectively [12,41]:

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{MB}} = \frac{\mathbf{u}^* \cdot \hat{n}}{4} \left[(\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2) \mathbf{E}_{p,\parallel}^* \cdot \mathbf{E}_{s,\parallel} - \left(\frac{1}{\varepsilon_1} - \frac{1}{\varepsilon_2} \right) \mathbf{D}_{p,\perp}^* \cdot \mathbf{D}_{s,\perp} \right], \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{PE}} = -\frac{\varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_1^2}{4} \mathbf{E}_p^* \cdot \mathbf{T}_{pe} : \mathbf{T}_s \cdot \mathbf{E}_s, \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{E} is the electric field, \mathbf{D} is the electric displacement, ε_1 is the permittivity of the core material, ε_2 is the permittivity of the cladding material, \mathbf{T}_{pe} is the photoelastic tensor and \mathbf{T}_s is the strain tensor. Finally, the mechanical quality factor (Q_m) reflects the energy loss of the mechanical mode. Different loss sources decrease the mechanical quality factor. We limit Q_m to a value of 1000 to consider different loss mechanisms of GHz phonons at ambient temperature and atmospheric pressure, such as inhomogeneous broadening (i.e., due to fabrication disorder in the waveguide geometry along its length) and thermo-viscous loss from surrounding air [45,46]. Other source of losses like the thermo-elastic loss and the phonon leakage to the adjacent Si slab in membrane waveguides is directly taken into consideration within COMSOL simulation software [47].

Regarding the materials, crystalline silicon and air are employed in our model as Brillouin waveguides are suspended from the BOX layer (which is typically achieved in fabrication by HF vapor baths). The main properties of the materials employed for the calculation of the Brillouin gain are summarized in Table 1. The design wavelength is centered at the middle of the C-band, that is, 1550 nm wavelength. It is important to highlight that the crystal structure of silicon is cubic and the designed waveguides are aligned with the 110 direction, i.e., they are rotated $\pi/4$ from the 100 direction in which the data was measured [40,48]. This precise orientation is important for accurately modeling the waveguide material as anisotropic, particularly since the waveguide orientation on our SOI wafers adheres to the 110 direction.

The validation of our model was previously carried out by matching the results of multi-physics simulations with experimental data retrieved from the measurements of fabricated devices [40]. The comparison between experiments and simulations shows an excellent agreement in terms of both mechanical frequency and Brillouin gain coefficient with slight deviations arising from fabrication uncertainties (e.g., typical over- or under-etching errors).

Table 1. Material properties of Si and air considered in the simulations^a [11,42]

Material property	Symbol	Unit	Silicon	Air
Refractive index	n	–	3.45	1
Density	ρ	$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$	2329	1293
Electrical conductivity	σ	$\text{S} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$	0	0
Photoelastic tensor	$[p_{11}, p_{12}, p_{44}]$	–	[-0.094, 0.017, -0.051]	–
Young's module	E	Pa	165.26×10^9	–
Poisson's ratio	ν	–	0.046	–
Thermal conductivity	κ	$\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$	150	0.02
Heat capacity	C_p	$\text{J} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$	700	1015
Sound speed	c_s	$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	9620	343.2
Elasticity tensor	$[c_{11}, c_{12}, c_{44}]$	Pa	$[166, 64, 79] \times 10^9$	–
Coefficient of thermal expansion	α	K^{-1}	2.57×10^{-6}	–
Bulk viscosity	μ_B	$\text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}$	–	1.85×10^{-5}
Dynamic viscosity	μ	$\text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}$	–	1.81×10^{-5}
Specific heat ratio	γ	–	–	1.4
Specific gas constant	R_s	$\text{J} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$	–	0.919
Mean molar mass	M_n	$\text{kg} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$	–	0.02896

^aValues at $T = 293 \text{ K}$ and $p = 1 \text{ atm}$.

3. Design and results

3.1. Suspended silicon waveguides based on subwavelength membranes

Most state-of-the-art optomechanical waveguides based on subwavelength membranes or rib waveguides are designed to operate with a transverse-electric (TE) polarized optical mode that couples to transverse mechanical modes with a predominant displacement profile in the same direction. For such optomechanical waveguides, the incorporation of anchoring arms or perforated slabs is necessary to remove the buried underlying SiO_2 and ensure mechanical stability after suspension. The primary limitation of this approach is the predominant interaction of both optical and acoustic modes with these lateral interfaces, which typically leads to increased propagation losses for the optical mode and leakage of the acoustic mode into the lateral Si slab. Although these effects have been effectively alleviated by judiciously designing the waveguide geometry, there are still trade-offs in the optomechanical overlap that ultimately limit the Brillouin gain. Here we propose three alternative designs that overcome this limitation and achieve an enhanced Brillouin gain by operating with a transverse-magnetic (TM) polarized optical mode and a vertically breathing mechanical mode.

Figure 1 shows the top view of three different silicon membrane waveguides based on a conventional strip waveguide (panel a), a slot waveguide (panel b), and a subwavelength grating slot waveguide (panel c). All designs share the geometrical parameters of the membrane, i.e. the width of the membrane W_M , the transversal period Λ_T , and the width and length of the holes, W_H and L_H , respectively.

The lateral index contrast (along the x -axis) is governed by the difference between the refractive indices in the core and the membrane. The width of the air holes in the membrane has a strong influence on the lateral confinement, e.g., larger holes reduce the metamaterial index and increase the lateral index contrast, enhancing the field confinement in the horizontal direction and reducing the lateral leakage. We set the hole dimensions to $W_H = 300 \text{ nm}$, $L_H = 190 \text{ nm}$, and $\Lambda_T = 420 \text{ nm}$

Fig. 1. (a) Top view schematic illustration of the proposed optomechanical waveguides based on lateral subwavelength membranes. Each design features a different geometry for the waveguide core: (a) conventional strip waveguide, (b) slot waveguide, and (c) SWG slot waveguide. The geometrical parameters for each waveguide are indicated within the schematic. The thickness of the silicon layer (y direction) is 300 nm and a single-etch step is considered for the design. k_p is the optical wavevector of the pump.

as a compromise between minimum feature size (MFS), mechanical stability, and index contrast between the core and membrane [49]. The horizontal distribution of the electric field component E_y was analyzed using 3D finite-difference time-domain (3D FDTD) simulations [50]. As shown in Fig. 2, the evanescent field begins to be negligible (<30 dB) for a distance of 1.5 μm from the center. Hence, the separation between the waveguide core and the silicon slab is set at $W_M = 2.52 \mu\text{m}$ to prevent light coupling into the silicon slab. Subsequently, the dimensions of the waveguide core were optimized for each of the designs by iterative simulations searching for the highest G_B . The optimal core width is $W_C = 260 \text{ nm}$ for the optomechanical strip waveguide, whereas for the slot and SWG slot waveguides the best performance was found for $W_R = 240 \text{ nm}$ and $G_R = 190 \text{ nm}$ and $W_S = 200 \text{ nm}$ and $G_S = 50 \text{ nm}$, respectively. Note that robust mechanical stability of fully suspended silicon slot waveguides has already been demonstrated, showing rail cores in the same horizontal plane for waveguides up to 8 mm in length [51]. Nevertheless, W_M could be reduced down to 1.5 μm to further increase the mechanical stability of the slot waveguide without compromising light confinement. Regarding the longitudinal period, we choose $\Lambda_L = 240 \text{ nm}$, below half of the effective optical wavelength, which allows the operation of the fundamental TM mode in the subwavelength regime. All the designs were also constrained to have a minimum feature size of 50 nm to ensure compatibility with electron-beam lithography.

Figure 3 shows the results obtained through full 3D optomechanical simulations for each optimized geometry. The optomechanical waveguide comprising a strip waveguide in Fig. 3(a) yields an outstanding Brillouin gain of $G_B = 12257 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ for a high mechanical frequency of $\Omega/(2\pi) = 12.67 \text{ GHz}$. In this case, the contribution of the moving boundaries effect ($4540 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$) is more than twice as large as the contribution of the photoelastic effect ($1877 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$) and the coherent combination of both effects enhances the FSBS process. The low duty cycle in the longitudinal ($\text{DC}_L = (\Lambda_L - L_H)/\Lambda_L = 0.21$) and transversal ($\text{DC}_T = (\Lambda_T - W_H)/\Lambda_T = 0.21$) directions contributes to a lower overall rigidity of the membrane and facilitates the compression and expansion of the silicon core. This allows the radiation pressure to exert vertical outward forces at the boundaries of the waveguide, which couples with the high field concentrations of the TM_0 mode at the discontinuous dielectric boundaries. The introduction of a gap to create a suspended slot waveguide does not markedly enhance the Brillouin gain, as the electric field maxima are on the top and bottom faces of the waveguide rails (W_R) as shown in Fig. 3(b). The

Fig. 2. Horizontal distribution of the electric field magnitude $|E_y|$ for (a) the strip, (b) the slot, and (c) the SWG slot optomechanical waveguides calculated at the center of the cell and mid-silicon height.

Fig. 3. Normalized electric field distribution (left column) and mechanical field displacement (right column) of the optimized optomechanical waveguides for (a) strip, (b) slot, and (c) SWG slot cores. Inset: spatial distribution of the moving boundary integrand.

Brillouin gain is reduced to $G_B = 5919 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ and the mechanical frequency to $\Omega/(2\pi) = 12.23$ GHz. This reduction in G_B can be attributed mainly to a lower contribution from the moving boundaries effect ($1505 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$). Finally, the waveguide based on an SWG slot subtly modifies the spatial distribution of the electric field towards the air gap. However, the incorporation of an extra arm connecting the two rails provides additional rigidity to the structure (as indicated by the normalized displacement in the membrane area), yielding a still remarkable Brillouin gain of $G_B = 5665 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ and a high mechanical frequency of $\Omega/(2\pi) = 13.18$ GHz. In all three scenarios, the dominance of the moving boundaries effect allows to overcome material limitations. This occurs as light propagation and scattering are manipulated at the nanoscale by geometry, rather than solely relying on material properties, providing additional degrees of freedom to control optomechanical interactions on chip. According to our non-linear theoretical model [40], net gain is achievable in the strip membrane considering a waveguide length of 5 mm, pump power ~ 35 mW and optical propagation loss of 3 dB/cm. Due to the lower Brillouin gain of the slot and SWG slot waveguides, net gain requires longer waveguides and higher pump power, i.e. a length of 6 mm and pump power ~ 50 mW for the slot waveguide and same length but a pump power ~ 60 mW for the SWG slot waveguide.

3.2. Fully suspended silicon waveguides

Membrane waveguides are limited in their Brillouin performance primarily by the anchoring arms that support the core, and this is especially true for breathing mechanical modes with a displacement profile in the same direction as the arms. Removing these arms to suspend the waveguide completely by the longitudinal ends is another strategy that has been proposed to increase Brillouin gain using strip [12] and slot geometries [52]. This avoids a path for the loss of phonons, which are confined due to the high impedance mismatch between silicon and air. In this section, we propose some design alternatives incorporating periodic structures to further improve the Brillouin gain coefficient.

The first design of a fully suspended optomechanical waveguide is shown in Fig. 4(a) in a 3D view, while a 2D schematic of the top view is shown in Fig. 4(b). The waveguide comprises a width W and a thickness of 220 nm, as well as a series of holes of dimensions W_H and L_H arranged along the waveguide with a period Λ . The fundamental TE-polarized optical mode is considered in the design to enhance the interaction with horizontal breathing mechanical modes and harness the additional degrees of freedom provided by the subwavelength slot in the middle of the waveguide. Thus, a waveguide width of $W = 460$ nm is selected for single-mode optical operation. In line with the designs of earlier membrane waveguides, the chosen periodicity ($\Lambda = 300$ nm) ensures that the structure operates within the subwavelength regime at the design wavelength of 1550 nm.

With all these initial geometrical parameters, the holes should be between 50 and 360 nm to comply with the MFS of 50 nm. Very narrow W_H values increase the stiffness of the structure's sidewalls, while very wide values can lead to unconfined optical modes that are almost at cut-off. We found a compromise for $W_H = 150$ nm. The length of the holes is then swept between 50 and 250 nm to maximize the Brillouin gain. Figure 5(a) shows the results obtained by optomechanical simulations. As expected, the minimum Brillouin gain is given for air holes with smaller widths, while the maximum value $G_B = 43542 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ is obtained for $L_H = 230$ nm and a mechanical frequency of 4.45 GHz. The main improvement in Brillouin gain stems from an enhanced moving boundaries effect ($20313 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$) that couples coherently with the photoelastic effect ($4375 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$). Interestingly, longer hole lengths do not result in higher Brillouin gain, due to a weak optical mode confinement that reduces the overlap with the mechanical mode. Furthermore, by changing L_H , the mechanical frequency can be tuned over a wide range between 4 and 9 GHz at the cost of lower gain for higher frequencies. Note that higher mechanical frequencies typically require optomechanical waveguides with small features or the support of higher-order

Fig. 4. (a) 3D schematic illustration showing the proposed optomechanical waveguide with subwavelength slot. (b) Top view schematic illustration of the simulated unit cell. The thickness of the silicon layer (y direction) is 220 nm and a single-etch step is considered for the design.

mechanical modes whose overlap with the optical mode is worse. Figures 5(c) and 5(d) display the distribution of the optical and mechanical fields for the refined design, where $L_H = 230$ nm. The high optical intensity in the SWG slot region is due to the major component of the TE_0 mode electric field (E_x) being oriented perpendicular to the slot boundaries, resulting in a strong overlap between mechanical and optical modes.

Fig. 5. (a) Brillouin gain and (b) frequency of the mechanical mode as a function of the air hole length, L_H . Normalized (c) electric field distribution and (d) mechanical field of the suspended silicon optomechanical waveguide with subwavelength slot. Inset: spatial distribution of the moving boundary integrand.

Such waveguides can only be suspended a few tens of micrometers before they collapse, which limits the interaction of optical and mechanical modes to a relatively short length compared to subwavelength silicon membranes. However, the unit cells can be inserted as defects into optical or optomechanical cavities to confine both modes and maximize their interaction [53]. Within the field of optomechanical cavities, one of the most relevant figures of merit to maximize is the optomechanical coupling rate, g_0 , defined as the rate at which the optical frequency of a cavity changes in response to a mechanical displacement [54]. For reference, the previously designed cell exhibits a high value of $g_0/(2\pi) = 4139$ kHz.

There are different strategies to increase Brillouin gain. One of them consists of introducing two lateral arms on the outer walls where the mechanical displacement occurs to favor the moving boundaries effect [see Fig. 6(a)-(c)]. Let us consider the same structure as in Fig. 4(b), i.e., with the same geometrical parameters but incorporating symmetric side arms with $W_A = 150$ nm, $L_A = 70$ nm. The calculated Brillouin gain for this new optomechanical waveguide is increased to $51949 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$, the frequency of the mechanical mode is reduced by 600 MHz concerning the mechanical frequency of the original counterpart and the optomechanical coupling rate is $g_0/(2\pi) = 4196$ kHz. This type of geometry comprising holes and side arms allows the realization of optomechanical cavities with simultaneous photonic and phononic band gaps [55,56]. The other strategy is to exploit the slow light using Bragg gratings or phoxonic crystals to create cavities [23,57]. This approach prevents the need for long lengths that reduce the risk of structural collapse and minimizes optical propagation losses. The expression of the Brillouin gain in Eq. (3) can be rewritten as follows [57]:

$$G_B = \frac{2\omega_p Q_m}{v_{gp} v_{gs} \Omega_m^2} \cdot \frac{|\langle \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u} \rangle|^2}{\langle \mathbf{E}_p, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \mathbf{E}_p \rangle \langle \mathbf{E}_s, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \mathbf{E}_s \rangle \langle \mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\rho} \mathbf{u} \rangle}, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{f} is the force distribution induced by the light and the notation $\langle \rangle$ signifies the integration of the inner production over a single unit cell. Light possessing low group velocities takes an extended duration to traverse a specified distance, resulting in a prolonged interaction period between light and matter. Thus, slow group velocities for the pump and scattered light would directly enhance the Brillouin gain. For example, we take our previously reported suspended waveguide [58] and include 50×50 nm holes in the center of the waveguide that are placed half a period shifted concerning the arms to further decrease the group velocity. The geometrical parameters of the optomechanical waveguide are schematically illustrated in Fig. 6(d) and comprise: a silicon thickness of 220 nm, $W = 340$ nm, $\Lambda = 460$ nm, $L_H = 230$ nm, $W_H = 400$ nm, $W_A = 50$ nm, and $L_A = 50$ nm. 3D simulations show that the Brillouin gain can be increased up to $17 \times 10^6 \text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ for a mechanical mode of 11.18 GHz, which is an order of magnitude higher than the Brillouin gain achieved by slot waveguide Bragg gratings. In addition, the optomechanical coupling rate reaches 1776 kHz.

Fig. 6. Top view schematic illustration of the (a) subwavelength slot optomechanical waveguide with lateral arms and (d) dual-Bragg waveguide. (b), (e) Normalized electric field distribution and (c), (f) mechanical field displacement. Inset: spatial distribution of the moving boundary integrand.

4. Discussion and conclusions

For the sake of comparison, Table 2 provides the performance of simulated state-of-the-art FBS suspended waveguides based on silicon wires surrounded by air. The suspended waveguides proposed in this work exhibit one of the highest coupling factors G_B/Q_m , comparable only to the work of Van Laer *et al.* [25], which utilizes a narrow pedestal waveguide to avoid phonon leakage towards the substrate at the cost of a more complex fabrication and a limited mechanical robustness. Our membrane waveguides address these limitations as they include anchoring arms to provide mechanical stability, and they rely on a standard silicon-on-insulator fabrication process and an HF vapor bath to release the structure. On the other hand, the proposed fully suspended waveguides achieve a G_B/Q_m of more than twice that of the current state of the art, with the slow-light-based waveguide yielding a remarkable 2.3-fold improvement. Consequently, our designs represent, to the best of our knowledge, some of the optomechanical waveguides with the highest Brillouin gain demonstrated to date for suspended silicon wires.

In conclusion, we have proposed different silicon optomechanical waveguides based on subwavelength membranes and fully suspended that achieve improved interplay between the acoustic mode and the optical mode. For subwavelength membranes, three different designs have been reported that operate with the fundamental TM mode to minimize phonon leakage losses through the arms connecting the core to the adjacent silicon slab. These designs comprise strip, slot, and SWG slot waveguides that achieve Brillouin gains of 12257, 5919, and 5665 $W^{-1}m^{-1}$, respectively, for high mechanical frequencies of 12-13 GHz. Regarding suspended silicon waveguides, a geometry that incorporates SWG in the center of the waveguide has also been reported. Since the path for the phonon leakage is removed, fundamental TE mode is employed to attain an optical intensity in the SWG slot region and better couple to the moving

Table 2. Comparison of simulated state-of-the-art FBS suspended waveguides based on silicon wires surrounded by air. Values marked with * were taken for a minimum feature size of 50 nm to be compatible with state-of-the-art fabrication processes

Type	Ref.	$\Omega/(2\pi)$ (GHz)	Q_m (-)	G_B/Q_m ($W^{-1}m^{-1}$)
Membranes	[25]	9.20	~60	~12.5
	[26]	4.41	1000	1.0
	[27]	9.40 & 9.70	1725	4.5 & 10.9
	[28]	5.90	-	<7.0
	[37]	3.69	2970	0.6
	[38]	~9.00	~700	4.3
	[39]	14.58	4000	0.8
	[40]	7.18	1000	2.0
	This work	12.67	1000	12.3
	This work	12.23	1000	5.9
	This work	13.18	1000	5.7
Fully suspended	[12]	13.00	1000	23.0
	[42]	27.11	1000	17.2
	[52]	~3.50	1000	10.0*
	This work	4.45	1000	43.5
	This work	3.84	1000	51.9
Fully suspended slow light	[23]	~5.00	1000	8.5
	[29]	~5.00	1000	2000.0
	[57]	12.65	1000	7330.0
	This work	11.18	1000	17250.0

boundaries effect. A considerable gain of $G_B = 43542 W^{-1}m^{-1}$ was obtained for $\Omega/(2\pi) = 4.45$ GHz. Furthermore, by modifying the hole length, it is possible to tune the mechanical frequency between 4 and 9 GHz. Finally, two strategies have been applied to improve the Brillouin gain: i) by including side arms to reinforce the moving boundaries effect on the inner walls of the holes and ii) by reducing the group velocity of light. The latter approach yields Brillouin gain values up to $17 \times 10^6 W^{-1}m^{-1}$ for an acoustic mode frequency of 11.18 GHz.

The results presented in this work show great potential for developing highly-efficient Brillouin waveguides and cavities. These improvements could reduce length and power requirements for initiating optomechanical interactions while achieving high mechanical frequencies. The next steps for suspended silicon waveguides based on subwavelength membranes include fabricating them for experimental validation. The use of new fabrication processes with more precise lithographic resolutions, such as immersion lithography or extreme-UV lithography, could also improve the uniformity of waveguide width and height, which in turn would reduce dimensional-induced resonance broadening. Finally, alternative designs with rounded corners could be explored for fully suspended waveguides in order to implement optomechanical cavities that incorporate the proposed unit cells.

Appendix A: robustness against fabrication disorder

To study the tolerance to fabrication disorders of the six proposed waveguide designs typical over- and under-etching errors that may occur during sample fabrication have been considered. As an

example, Fig. 7 shows the geometries resulting from applying over-etching (panel a, red dashed lines) and under-etching (panel b, blue dashed lines) to the fully suspended optomechanical waveguide with subwavelength slot. For under-etching errors the width of the waveguide becomes $W = W + \Delta\delta$, while the width and length of the air holes are $W_H = W_H - \Delta\delta$ and $L = L_H - \Delta\delta$, respectively. The opposite occurs for over-etching errors, where the waveguide is shrunk, and the holes are enlarged by a factor $\Delta\delta$. It should be noted that, although the periodicity of the structure is not typically affected by this type of fabrication disorder, the duty cycle of the periodic region, i.e. $DC = (\Lambda - L_H)/\Lambda$, is modified through the change in the length of the air holes.

Fig. 7. Top view schematic illustrations of the first fully suspended optomechanical waveguide design for (a) over- and (b) under-etching errors that typically occur during fabrication. Brillouin gain as a function of the fabrication error for thickness (purple) and etching (blue) variations of the optomechanical waveguides based on lateral subwavelength membranes with (c) conventional strip core, (d) slot core, and (e) SWG slot core. Brillouin gain as a function of the fabrication error for thickness (purple) and etching (blue) variations of the fully suspended optomechanical waveguides based on (f) subwavelength slot, (g) subwavelength slot with lateral arms, and (h) dual Bragg.

Based on this approach, we have studied the robustness of the six proposed waveguides against fabrication disorder. Additionally, we have studied the effect of variations in silicon thickness. Figure 7(c)-(e) and 7(f)-(h) show the simulated Brillouin gains for thickness and etching errors of $\Delta\delta = \pm 2\text{nm}$ of suspended Si waveguides based on subwavelength membranes and fully suspended Si waveguides, respectively. For the membrane-based optomechanical waveguides [see Fig. 7(c)-(e)], the degradation of the Brillouin gain is barely noticeable. Considering the worst value for each device, G_B values remain consistently above $11729\text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ for the strip core waveguide, $5876\text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ for the slot core waveguide and $5376\text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ for the SWG slot waveguide. On the other hand, the minimum G_B for fully suspended waveguides [see Fig. 7(f)-(h)] is $39810\text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ for the one based on a subwavelength slot, $51258\text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ for the one based on a subwavelength slot with lateral arms and $16.59 \times 10^6\text{ W}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$ for the dual Bragg waveguide. These results demonstrate the robustness of our solutions to fabrication disorders such as typically over- and under-etching, and thickness variations.

Funding. RENATECH; General Council of Essonne; HORIZON EUROPE European Research Council (101087901, ERC-SPRING); HORIZON EUROPE Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (101062518, MSCA-SUNRISE).

Acknowledgments. This work has been funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe (Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement N° 101062518) and the European Union (ERC-SPRING, under the Grant Agreement 101087901). This work was done within the C2N micro nanotechnologies platforms and partly supported by the RENATECH network and the General Council of Essonne. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Disclosures. The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data availability. The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at [59].

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